

An Expression for the Evaluation of Partition Coefficient in Countercurrent Distribution

S. B. Ghosh, R. K. Sinha, and P. Nandi

The advantages and difficulties of the different methods for calculating K from the experimental distribution band have been discussed. A formula relating K with $r_{\max}$ and n has been deduced from the binomial relation without neglecting $r_{\max}$ in comparison with n , as Nichols did. The limitations of the formula, which holds good for K , much deviated from unity and at a comparatively small value of n , have been analysed in detail. The cause of deviation of the formula for a very high or low value of K has been explained. The formula approaches Craig's as n approaches ∞ or K approaches unity, i.e., at the condition where binomial distribution approaches the Gaussian. The range of usefulness of the formula has been compared with Craig's considering the theoretical distribution patterns obtained from the B. P. D. Tables, as well as the experimental distribution bands of succinic acid between amyl alcohol and water ($K \ll 1$) and neutral red between butanol² and 1% HCl ($K \ll 1$).

In order to calculate the theoretical distribution band, it is of primary importance to know the exact value of the partition coefficient of the distributed material. Besides, in case of a binary mixture, the partition coefficients of the individual components should be accurately known for the prediction of the degree of separation for a particular number of transfers. The preference of calculating K from the experimental distribution band to its determination from single partition study has been discussed by Craig and Craig ("Technique of Organic Chemistry", edited by Weissberger, 1950, Vol. III, pp. 171-211, Interscience Publishers, New York).

Of the different expressions concerning K (Craig, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1944, 155, 519; Williamson and Craig, *ibid.*, 1947, 168, 687; Lieberman, *ibid.*, 1948, 178, 63; Bacher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 1023), mostly used is that of Craig.

$$K r_{\max} = \frac{nK}{K+1} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

from which it follows:

$$K = \frac{r_{\max}}{n - r_{\max}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

It is an approximate relation and becomes exact only if K is equal to 1 or if there is an infinite number of transfers (Williamson and Craig, *loc. cit.*). In case of a finite number of transfers and where the partition coefficient deviates considerably from unity on either side, the calculated K value deviates considerably from the actual; hence considerable trials are needed in order to fit the theoretical distribution curve with the experimental one. In these cases, the necessity of more accurate calculations based on binomial expansion has been recognised (Gregory and Craig, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1951, 53, 1015).

The method due to Williamson and Craig (*loc. cit.*) has the advantage that the ratio of concentration in two adjacent tubes in any part of the distribution band can be used for the calculation of K . This method is suitable for the determination of K of individual components of a binary mixture from tubes lying on the slope of the distribution band when the peak regions do not contain pure solute or even resolution of the peaks is not effected. But the method fails to give accurate K value in case of heterogeneous solute, where the ratio of $T_{n,r}$ values in the two adjacent tubes does not correspond to the ratio of their total concentrations. This difficulty, however, may be removed if a highly specific analytical method of determination of the solute in question is available. The calculation of K according to Lieberman (*loc. cit.*) is easy to perform with a calculating machine. It should be noted here that Lieberman directly differentiated the logarithmic form of equation (3), viz.,

$$T_{n,r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!} \frac{1}{(K+1)^n} \cdot K^r \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

with respect to r without assuming Stirling's approximation. Consequently, it is not possible to accommodate in his treatment the peak in the hypothetical fractional tube.

The method due to Bacher (*loc. cit.*) is statistically perfect and provides the best method of calculating K in the case of a homogeneous solute. But since all the tubes may not always contain pure solute, the experimental value of the first or the second mean cannot be accurately determined unless a highly specific analytical method of determination of the solute concerned is available. Unlike this method, the others require the solute to be pure either in the tubes at the peak region of the distribution band or in any two adjacent tubes.

The methods due to Williamson and Craig (*loc. cit.*), Lieberman (*loc. cit.*), and Bacher (*loc. cit.*) have no doubt an advantage over that due to the earlier method of Craig (*loc. cit.*) of determining K values from the distribution band even when the peak is attained in the o th or n th tube, but owing to its simplicity Craig's method is often preferred. Moreover, when the number of transfers is high, Craig's expression for K becomes exact, if K is not too high or too low. It is, of course, expedient to check the K value by calculating it directly from the analysis of the tube corresponding to the peak or any other region.

Theoretical Considerations

Nichols (*Anal. Chem.*, 1950, **22**, 915) deduced equation (1) from equation (3) and pointed out the approximations involved in the deduction. He differentiated the logarithmic form of equation (3), set the derivative equal to zero, and obtained equation (4), when $r = r_{\max}$, the tube number where peak of the distribution band is reached.

$$\frac{n+0.5}{n} + \ln \frac{n}{n-r_{\max}} - \frac{n-r_{\max}+0.5}{n-r_{\max}} + \ln \frac{1}{K+1} = 0 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

When n is large with respect to $r_{\max}$, the first and the third terms in the left hand side of equation (4) cancel out and on simplification, equation (4) reduces to equation (1). The following points may be noted in connection with the above derivation:

(1) The formula given by Craig is an approximate one and becomes exact only when either n tends to infinity or K becomes unity (Williamson and Craig, *loc. cit.*). The first

condition justifies the omission of $r_{\max}$ in the third term of the left hand side of equation (4); but at $K=1$, $r_{\max}$ becomes $0.5n$, which cannot be neglected in comparison with n .

(2) When $K \gg 1$, $r_{\max}$ in equation (4) cannot be neglected in comparison with n and equation (1) does not hold good. But when $K \ll 1$, $r_{\max}$ in equation (4) can be neglected in comparison with n and equation (1) can be derived, but in this case equation (1) does not hold good as well. If $r_{\max}$ is put equal to zero, this would mean no distribution at all. This can also be seen by putting $r_{\max}=0$ in equation (4), when K becomes equal to zero.

The above analysis clearly suggests that $r_{\max}$ must not be neglected in comparison with n if an exact value of K is desired. In view of this it is found expedient, following Lieberman (*loc. cit.*), to differentiate equation (3) with respect r and not to n .

To do this, equation (3) is written in the form:

$$T_{n,r} = C \cdot \frac{1}{r!} \cdot \frac{K^r}{(n-r)!}$$

Where

$$C = \frac{n!}{(K+1)^n} \text{ is constant.}$$

Taking logarithms,

$$\ln T_{n,r} = \ln C - \ln r! + r \ln K - \ln(n-r)!$$

Using Stirling's approximation,

$$\ln T_{n,r} = \ln C - 0.5 \ln 2\pi - (\tau + 0.5) \ln r + r + r \ln K - 0.5 \ln 2\pi - (n - r + 0.5) \ln(n - r) + n - r.$$

Differentiating with respect to r , n remaining constant,

$$\frac{d(\ln T_{n,r})}{dr} = \ln K - \ln \frac{r}{n-r} + \frac{r-0.5n}{r(n-r)} \dots \quad (5)$$

Setting the derivative equal to zero, when $r=r_{\max}$, and rearranging

$$\begin{aligned} \ln K &= \ln \frac{r_{\max}}{n-r_{\max}} - \frac{r_{\max}-0.5n}{r_{\max}(n-r_{\max})} \\ K &= \frac{r_{\max}}{n-r_{\max}} \cdot e^{-(r_{\max}-0.5n)/r_{\max}(n-r_{\max})} \dots \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

That $r_{\max}$ is the tube number, where the maximum of the distribution curve lies, can be shown by differentiating equation (5) with respect to r and rearranging.

$$\frac{d^2(\ln T_{n,r})}{dr^2} = \frac{-r(n-r)(1+n) + 0.5n^2}{r^2(n-r)^2} \dots \quad (7)$$

If this value of r should represent $r_{\max}$, the second derivative ought to be negative. The denominator of the right hand side of the equation involving square terms is always positive. As $r > n$, the first term of the numerator is always negative; the second term is always positive. The limiting value of r , for which the numerator becomes negative, should be

such as to give amongst others a $-0.5n^2$ term. This can be achieved by substituting r either by 0.5 or $(n-0.5)$. In either case, equation (7) is reduced to

$$\frac{d^2 (\ln T_{n,r})}{dr^2} = \frac{1-n}{(n-0.5)^2} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Since for a binomial distribution n should be at least 2, equation (8) is always negative.

But if r is substituted either by $0.5 - x$ or $n - (0.5 - x)$ where $x > 0.5$ (*i.e.*, at the limiting value of x , r is either equal to 0 or n), equation (7) is reduced to

$$\frac{d^2 (\ln T_{n,r})}{dr^2} = \frac{-0.25n + 0.25 - x + x^2 + n^2x + nx^2}{(0.5-x)^2 \{ n - (0.5-x) \}^2} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

The right hand side, as can be easily shown, is always positive for any value of x within its limiting value, *i.e.* 0.5.

The above analysis therefore shows that the second derivative of $\ln T_{n,r}$ (cf eq. 7) is negative, *i.e.*, a maximum will occur only if $(n-0.5) \gg r \gg 0.5$. Consequently, calculation of K based on $r_{\max}$ with the help of equation (6) is significant if $r_{\max}$ occurs within the above range, *viz.*, $(n-0.5)$ and 0.5 . Unlike equation (1) or (2), equation (6) has been derived, using Stirling's approximation, but without neglecting $r_{\max}$ compared to n and is therefore more exact.

Moreover, equation (6) reduces to equation (2) if the exponential term is unity, or in other words, the exponent is zero. This is so, if $r_{\max} = n/2$ or $n = \infty$, which would respectively mean that $K=1$ and n is large. These are exactly the conditions under which equation (2) becomes exact. Equation (6), which is based only on the condition: $(n-0.5n) \gg r \gg 0.5$, is therefore expected to be more accurate, as shown by the data recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Comparison of the theoretical and the calculated K values.

Number of transfers, $n = 24$.

p .	$r_{\max}$.	K (B.P.D. Tables).	K (eq. 6).	K (eq. 2).	p .	$r_{\max}$.	K (B.P.D. Tables).	K (eq.6).	K (eq.2).
0.04	0.5	0.0417	0.0566	0.0213	0.52	12.5	1.0833	1.0832	1.9870
0.08	1.5	0.0870	0.0910	0.0667	0.56	13.5	1.2727	1.2722	1.2857
0.12	2.5	0.1364	0.1388	0.1163	0.60	14.5	1.5000	1.4989	1.5263
0.16	3.5	0.1905	0.1922	0.1707	0.64	15.5	1.7778	1.7757	1.8235
0.20	4.5	0.2500	0.2514	0.2308	0.68	16.5	2.1250	2.1214	2.2000
0.24	5.5	0.3158	0.3169	0.2973	0.72	17.5	2.5714	2.5651	2.6923
0.28	6.5	0.3889	0.3898	0.3714	0.76	18.5	3.1667	3.1554	3.3636
0.32	7.5	0.4706	0.4714	0.4545	0.80	19.5	4.0000	3.9782	4.3333
0.36	8.5	0.5625	0.5632	0.5484	0.84	20.5	5.2500	5.2026	5.8571
0.40	9.5	0.6667	0.6671	0.6552	0.88	21.5	7.3333	7.2071	8.6000
0.44	10.5	0.7857	0.7861	0.7778	0.92	22.5	11.5000	10.9897	15.0000
0.48	11.5	0.9231	0.9232	0.9200	0.96	23.5	24.0000	17.6626	47.0000
0.50	12.0	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000					

TABLE II

*Comparison of the theoretical and the calculated K values.*Number of transfers, $n = 49$.

p .	$r_{\max}$.	K (B.P.D. Tables).	$K(\text{eq.6})$.	$K(\text{eq.2})$.	p .	$r_{\max}$.	K (B.P.D. Tables).	$K(\text{eq.6})$.	$K(\text{eq.2})$.
0.02	0.5	0.0204	0.0277	0.0103	0.50	24.5	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000
0.04	1.5	0.0417	0.0436	0.0316	0.52	25.5	1.0933	1.0933	1.0651
0.06	2.5	0.0638	0.0650	0.0539	0.54	26.5	1.1730	1.1730	1.7778
0.10	4.5	0.1111	0.1117	0.1011	0.58	28.5	1.3810	1.3808	1.3902
0.14	6.5	0.1628	0.1632	0.1529	0.62	30.5	1.6316	1.6313	1.6486
0.18	8.5	0.2195	0.2199	0.2099	0.66	32.5	1.9412	1.9404	1.9697
0.22	10.5	0.2821	0.2823	0.2727	0.70	34.5	2.3333	2.3322	2.3793
0.26	12.5	0.3514	0.3516	0.3425	0.74	36.5	2.8462	2.8442	2.9200
0.30	14.5	0.4286	0.4288	0.4203	0.78	38.5	3.5455	3.5420	3.6667
0.34	16.5	0.5152	0.5153	0.5077	0.82	40.5	4.5556	4.5483	4.7647
0.38	18.5	0.6129	0.6130	0.6066	0.86	42.5	6.1429	6.1258	6.5385
0.42	20.5	0.7241	0.7242	0.7193	0.90	44.5	9.0000	8.9487	9.9869
0.46	22.5	0.8519	0.8519	0.8401	0.94	46.5	15.6667	15.3938	18.6000
0.48	23.5	0.9231	0.9231	0.9216	0.96	47.5	21.0000	22.9306	31.6667
					0.98	48.5	49.0000	36.0539	67.0000

DISCUSSION

Tables I and II present the values of K calculated according to equations (2) and (6) for different values of $r_{\max}$, as shown in the B. P. D. Tables ("Tables of the Binomial Probability Distribution", National Bureau of Standards, Applied Mathematics Series; Washington) for 24 and 49 transfers respectively. The calculated K values are compared with those evaluated from the values of p provided in the B. P. D. Tables (Way and Bennett, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, **192**, 335). All the K values are rounded up to the fourth place of decimal. A slight defect in drawing the experimental curve may change the exact position of the peak in the hypothetical fractional tube and thus change the calculated K values considerably. This difficulty has been removed by choosing only those distribution values from the B. P. D. Tables where two successive tubes give the same value of the distributed material and the peak is assumed to be situated in between the two tubes. But when fractions in the two tubes separated by a single tube have the same value, the peak is assumed to be half way between the two.

For example, when $n=24$ and $p=0.20$ (*i.e.*, $K=0.25$), it is seen from the B. P. D. Tables that the fractions distributed at $r=4$ and $r=5$ have the same value, *viz.*, 0.1960151. Hence $r_{\max}$ is taken as 4.5. Now substituting the values of n and $r_{\max}$ in equation (6), $K=0.23077 \cdot e^{0.06347}=0.2514$. It will be observed that the K values calculated from equation (6) is in better agreement with those in the B. P. D. Tables than those calculated from equation (2).

For values of $K > 1$, *i.e.*, $p > 0.5$, equations (2) and (6) are replaced by equations (2a) and (6a) respectively (*cf.* Way and Bennett, *loc. cit.*).

$$K = \frac{n - r_{\max}}{r_{\max}} \quad \dots \quad (2a)$$

$$K = \frac{n - r_{\max}}{r_{\max}} \cdot e^{-(0.5 n - r_{\max})/r_{\max} \cdot (n - r_{\max})} \quad \dots \quad (6a)$$

Here also the agreement between the values calculated with equation (6a) and B. P. D. Tables is much better than that with equation (2a). At higher values of p or K , the agreement is poor. A comparison of Tables I and II shows that the difference between the two equations becomes less, when $n=49$, than when $n=24$. Furthermore, the difference between equations (2) and (2a) and B. P. D. Tables is much wider at lower and higher values of $r_{\max}$ compared to the corresponding difference between equations (6) and (6a) and B. P. D. Tables. The difference is less and less as $p \rightarrow 0.5$, *i.e.*, $r_{\max} \rightarrow n/2$, or $K \rightarrow 1$. At $p=0.5$, or $r_{\max} = n/2$, or $K=1$, all the K values are obviously identical.

It may be noted that Stirling's approximation should be assumed only for high numbers. In case of the logarithmic form of equation (3), assumption of the same approximation introduces considerable error when r approaches 0 and n , for then the magnitudes of r and $(n-r)!$ become small. In equation (2) this inaccuracy is combined with the inaccuracy of neglecting $r_{\max}$ in comparison with n , specially when $r_{\max}$ approaches n .

The limiting values of $r_{\max}$, *i.e.*, 0.5 and $(n-0.5)$, show the limiting values of K , which can be calculated with the help of equation (6) for a particular number of transfers. Tables I and II show that the ranges of values of K are from 0.0566 to 17.6626 for $n=24$ and 0.0277 to 36.0529 for $n=49$. This suggests that in order to obtain a theoretical curve for a substance having a very high or low partition coefficient, the number of transfers applied should be sufficiently high. Again, the limiting values of K are expected to have a maximum deviation from the corresponding actual K values. But the limiting values of K for a particular number of transfers applied deviate more and more from the limiting values of K as the number of transfers applied becomes higher and higher. Thus higher the number of transfers applied for a solute having very low or high K values, the more accurate should be its theoretical curve.

As the binomial distribution is a statistical distribution, the applicability of equations (2) and (6) may be discussed from the statistical viewpoint. If a unimodal distribution can be fitted with a smooth frequency curve, the mode is defined as the abscissa of the highest point on the curve, *i.e.*, $r_{\max}$ in countercurrent distribution curve. But for a binomial distribution, the mean number of success, *i.e.*, the mean position of the distribution curve is equal to the probability of success, p , in a single trial multiplied by the number of trials, n (cf. Bock, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4269), that is,

$$m = np = \frac{nK}{K+1} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

Craig equated the mode of distribution with its mean position, which is only true for a symmetrical distribution, *i.e.*, when K is equal to 1 or n is infinity. Bacher (*loc. cit.*) equated the observed and the theoretical mean of binomial distribution to evaluate K . But equation (6) is deduced on the basis of equality of the theoretical and the observed mode of binomial distribution. In fact, the observed mode, $r_{\max}$, is not evaluated as it is difficult to solve for $r_{\max}$ in equation (6). Hence equation (6), like that of Bacher, is sound from the statistical viewpoint.

Like all other equations relating K , equation (6) cannot give an accurate value of K if the peak region is not homogeneous. In that case a highly specific method of analysis of the solute concerned is essential. Notwithstanding this difficulty, equation (6) should be helpful in the calculation of K values much deviated from 1 on either side of a comparatively small number of transfers, where equation (2) fails.

Tube number.

FIG. 1.

A—experimental.

B—theoretical (K from eq. 2)C— " (K from eq. 6)

Tube number.

FIG. 2.

A'—experimental.

B'—theoretical (K from eq. 2).C'— " (K from eq. 6).

In order to test the validity of equation (6), two solutes were so chosen that K of one was much less and that of the other much greater than unity. In Fig. 1, curve A gives an experimental distribution band of 10 mg. of succinic acid distributed between water and amyl alcohol. The fractions were analysed by titration with $N/30$ -NaOH solution and $r_{\max}$ was found to be 2.7. Curves B and C are theoretical curves calculated on the basis of $K=0.13300$ and 0.15618 according to equation (2) and (6), respectively. In Fig. 2, curve A' shows an experimental distribution band of 1.3 mg. of neutral red distributed between butanol^{1a} and 1% HCl solution. The fractions were analysed spectrophotometrically (max. absorption at $540\text{ m}\mu$). $r_{\max}$ was found to be 20.6. Curves B' and C' are the theoretical curves calculated on the basis of $K=8.5835$ and 7.1402 according to equations (2) and (6), respectively. 23 transfers were used in both. Absolute ethanol was used as co-solvent in both the cases.

It is seen that curves C and C' have a closer agreement with curves A and A' respectively than with curves B and B'. The deviations in the trailing parts of the curves are probably due to the non-linearity of the partition isotherm of the solute distributed. In Fig. 2, curve B' only touches curve A' at the point corresponding to the 21st tube where it is fitted. In Fig. 1, though the peak of curve A falls at a hypothetical fractional tube, $r_{\max} = 2.7$, due to the drawing of a smooth curve, tube number 3 will in reality have the maximum concentration of the distributed material. Curve C has also the maximum concentration of the solute in tube number 3, but curve B surprisingly enough has maximum concentration in tube number 2. Moreover, curves B and B' fail to reproduce the peaks in the hypothetical tubes of their corresponding experimental distribution, since they are fitted in the position of the peaks of the real tubes.

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MICROBIOLOGICAL LABORATORY,
BOSE INSTITUTE,
CALCUTTA.

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